

REVIEW ARTICLE ABOUT HELICOBACTER PYLORI

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Abstract: Helicobacter pylori is a Gram-negative, 0.5-1 μm wide and 2-4 μm long, short spiral microorganism. It is found mostly in the pyloric region of the stomach and causes chronic gastric infection. It is estimated that this bacterium infects more than half of the world's population. The exact mode of transmission of H. pylori infection is still unknown, but fecal-oral routes through water or food consumption are thought to be a very common cause. In the past three decades, research interest has increased regarding pathogenesis, bacterial activity, genetic predisposition, and clinical treatments to understand the severity of gastric atrophy and gastric cancer caused by H. pylori. Studies have suggested an association between H. pylori infection and malabsorption of essential micronutrients, and have noted that H. pylori infection may influence the prevalence of malnutrition in some at-risk groups. On the other hand, dietary factors may play a major role in H. pylori infection, and an adequate and balanced diet, especially high consumption of fruits and vegetables and low consumption of processed salty foods, has been reported to have a protective effect against the outcomes of H. pylori infection. The present review provides an overview of all aspects of H. pylori infection, such as clinical features, treatment, and nutrition.

Introduction:

Helicobacter pylori was first identified in the stomach of dogs as a spiral microorganism by Giulio Pizzozero in 1892. Because it is a spiral microorganism similar to Campylobacter, it was named Campylobacter pyloridis by Barry Marshall and Robin Warren in 1983[1]. Goodwin et al. named it "Helicobacter pylori" in 1989, because of its spiral structure and it is mostly found in the pyloric region of the stomach. H. pylori is 0.5–1 μm wide, 2–4 μm long, a short, S-shaped, Gram-negative, spiral microorganism that infects more than half of the world's population. The relationship between H. pylori and gastric cancer was investigated in 1991 and 1994, and the International Agency for Research on Cancer, a branch of the World Health Organization, stated that H. pylori is a human carcinogen, which was confirmed in 2009 on the basis of epidemiological data [2]. In the United States, the National Institutes of Health reported in 1994 that H. pylori may be the major cause of peptic ulcer disease and should be treated. Marshall and Warren were awarded the Nobel Prize in Physiology or Medicine in 2005 for their work on H.

pylori "for the discovery of the role of *H. pylori* in gastritis and peptic ulcer disease." *H. pylori* plays a role in the development of diseases such as gastritis and membrane-associated lymphoid tissue (MALT) disease, as well as peptic ulcer disease and gastric cancer [3]. The exact mode of transmission of *H. pylori* is not known, but fecal-oral routes through water or food consumption are thought to be a very common cause [4]. The incidence of *H. pylori* infection increases with age. The rate of development is higher in communities with low socioeconomic status. The fact that *H. pylori* lives in the stomach and causes chronic inflammation shows that it can be resistant to both the immune response and acid. Many antibiotic treatments are used to treat *H. pylori*, and studies show that the number of strains resistant to the antibiotics used in treatment is rapidly increasing, which has led to the search for alternative agents to produce safer and more effective results in addition to antibiotic treatments [5]. Dietary factors are thought to play a significant role in *H. pylori* infection, and it has been reported that a proper and balanced diet, especially the consumption of fruits and vegetables in large quantities and abundance, has a protective effect against *H. pylori* outcomes [6]. However, some studies have suggested an association between *H. pylori* infection and malabsorption of essential micronutrients, and malnutrition may be prevalent in some groups in the long term [7]. This study aimed to discuss the general clinical features of *H. pylori* and its relationship to nutrition, as well as therapeutic practices related to the disease.

Description of *H. pylori*

Helicobacter pylori is a bacterium (germ) that can infect the human stomach. Its importance to human disease was first recognized in 1983. The bacteria live in the lining of the stomach, and the chemicals they produce cause inflammation of the stomach lining. The infection appears to last a lifetime unless treated with medications to kill the bacteria. These germs can enter your body and live in your digestive system. After many years, they can cause ulcers in the lining of your stomach or the upper part of your small intestine. For some people, the infection can lead to stomach cancer. *H. pylori* infection is common in countries with poor sanitation. It is estimated that more than 50% of the world's population has *H. pylori* in their upper digestive tract. For most people, it does not cause ulcers or any other symptoms. If you do have problems, there are medications that can kill the germs and help the ulcers heal. As more of the world gets access to clean water and sanitation, fewer people are getting infected with the bacteria than before. With good hygiene, you can protect yourself and your children from stomach bugs [8].

Researchers aren't sure how *H. pylori* is transmitted. It's most likely acquired in childhood, but how it happens isn't known. For decades, doctors thought people got ulcers from stress, spicy foods, smoking, or other lifestyle habits. But when scientists discovered *H. pylori* in 1982, they found that the bacterium is the cause of most stomach ulcers.

After *H. pylori* enters your body, it attacks the lining of your stomach, which normally protects you from the acid your body uses to digest food. Once the bacteria have done enough damage, the acid can penetrate the lining, leading to ulcers. They can bleed, cause infections, or prevent food from moving through your digestive tract [9]. *H. pylori* can be spread through food or water. The bacteria is most common in countries or communities that lack clean water or good sanitation. The bacteria can also be spread through contact with the saliva or other bodily fluids of infected people. Many people become infected with *H. pylori* as children, but adults can get it, too. The bacteria live in the body for years before symptoms start, but most people who are infected will never get ulcers. Doctors aren't sure why only some people get ulcers after they're infected [10].

Physiology of stomach bacteria (*H. Pylori*)

This bacteria lives and multiplies in the walls lining the stomach, infecting the stomach and small intestine. In many cases, this infection does not cause any harm to the infected person. However, in some other cases, this bacterium may attack the mucous layer lining the stomach that protects it from stomach acid, which

leads to the acid reaching the stomach wall. The bacteria grow in the patient's digestive system where it attacks the stomach lining, which in turn causes stomach irritation as a result of the effect of acid and bacteria. These bacteria break down the mucous wall of the stomach and duodenum, causing severe inflammation of the stomach and duodenum or the formation of ulcers or gastritis or stomach cancer. *Helicobacter pylori* is one of the main causes of inflammation in the stomach and duodenum. [11]. The reason for this is that this type of bacteria has the ability to live in the stomach because it is equipped with defenses that protect it from stomach acid, as this bacteria produces large amounts of the enzyme Urease helps bacteria survive in the harsh environment of the stomach, as the urease enzyme reacts with urea to produce ammonia, which is enough to neutralize stomach acidity. These bacteria infect the protective tissues lining the stomach, leading to the release of some enzymes and toxins, which directly or indirectly infect the cells of the stomach or duodenum. Over time, the stomach and duodenum wall become chronically inflamed, exposing them to damage caused by digestive juices such as stomach acid. These bacteria are also a common cause of ulcers in all patients, as 50% of people suffer from ulcers (Ulcers), which is one of the most common bacteria worldwide, but the symptoms of the stomach bacteria do not appear and infection with it is not dangerous in most cases. It may later develop into complex stages of stomach cancer, but 80% of those infected with this bacterium do not show symptoms. The stomach bacteria can live in the body for years before symptoms begin, and it may remain in the bodies of some people without causing any symptoms or causing stomach ulcers.[12]

Epidemiology of *H. pylori* infection

There are several studies on the prevalence, risk factors and pathways of *H. pylori* infection [13]. It is claimed that half of the world's population is infected with *H. pylori*, but it is clear that more evidence-based research is still needed. The incidence of this infection is higher in low socioeconomic status groups and developing countries. Vilaichone et al. found that the prevalence of *H. pylori* varies not only from country to country but also in different regions of the same country. It is difficult to determine its prevalence, as there is no health system that collects registry-based results of *H. pylori* prevalence in developing countries [14]. According to regional prevalence estimates, approximately 4.4 billion people are infected with *H. pylori* worldwide. The countries with the highest prevalence of *H. pylori* compared to the general population were found in Nigeria, Portugal, Estonia, Kazakhstan and Pakistan, and the lowest prevalence was in Switzerland. In a study by Mezmale et al. (2020), a high prevalence of *H. pylori* infection has been identified in Russia, Jordan, Iran, China, Canada, and Latin American countries [15]. Studies conducted in Turkey show that the prevalence of *H. pylori* infection is high. For example, in a study conducted by Uyaniko ğlu et al. in 2010, 918 patients out of 1298 patients who underwent biopsy were positive for *H. pylori* infection. The prevalence of *H. pylori* infection is similar in males and females, and the incidence of *H. pylori* infection is 73.2% between the ages of 14 and 30, 71.5% between the ages of 31 and 45, 68.6% between the ages of 46 and 60, and 70.4% between the ages of 61 and 88 [16]. In a study conducted by Özen et al. In 2011, 161 out of 473 children studying in four different primary and secondary schools in Istanbul were found to be infected with *H. pylori*. Similarly, Özaydın et al. screened 4622 individuals for *H. pylori* infection in 55 cities using C-urea breath test in 2013, and found that 3852 individuals (2075 females and 1777 males) were found to be *H. pylori* positive. In the review by Hooi et al., three studies were reported to have been conducted in Turkey until 2015, the total number of participants was 6036, and the prevalence was 77.2%. In a study by Soylu et al. In 2019, 46 patients (21 females and 25 males) were found to be infected with *H. pylori* in biopsy samples taken from 88 patients (53 females and 35 males) aged 18–77 years with complaints of dyspepsia. Compared to the total number of participants, male patients were found to be more positive for *H. pylori*. A study conducted in Nepal reported that 18.2% of children aged 6–59 months, 14% of boys and 16% of girls aged 10–19 years, and 40% of non-pregnant women aged 20–49 years were infected with *H. pylori*. [17]

H. pylori and chronic gastritis

Inflammation of the gastric lining associated with mucosal damage is defined as gastritis. It has been determined that the most common cause of chronic gastritis worldwide is *Helicobacter pylori* infection. The production of proinflammatory cytokines and inflammation caused by *H. pylori* infection affect gastrin-producing G cells, somatostatin-producing D cells, and acid-producing parietal cells, leading to significant changes in gastric acid balance [41][42]. Gastritis caused by *H. pylori* also decreases somatostatin levels. Since somatostatin negatively affects gastrin secretion, it causes increased gastrin levels and increased gastric acid secretion in these patients. Gastrin expression may be enhanced by the direct stimulatory effect of proinflammatory cytokines caused by *H. pylori* on G cells [40]. Reactive nitrogen species are produced by neutrophils/monocytes in response to *H. pylori* infection. These have the potential to cause DNA damage. DNA damage is thought to trigger a cascade of events in gastric carcinogenesis, which is gastritis-atrophy-metaplasia-dysplasia-cancer sequence, by causing mutations in some important genes in gastric tissue [43].

H. pylori and gastric cancer

Risk factors for gastric cancer, the fifth leading type of cancer worldwide and the third leading cause of cancer-related death worldwide, include *H. pylori* infection, high salt intake, and low fruit and vegetable intake. *H. pylori* pathogenesis and bacterial factors, including urease, VacA, CagA, and peptidoglycan outer membrane proteins, affect gastric epithelial cells. In addition, host genetics are affected by *H. pylori* infection, which affects genes encoding cytokines such as IL-8, IL-1 β , IL-10, and TNF- α that cause polymorphism and increase inflammatory responses, leading to the risk of gastric cancer. Thus, gastric cancer is not only affected by the characteristics of *H. pylori* strain, but also by host genetic determinants and environmental factors. It has also been shown that one of the environmental factors associated with an increased risk of gastric cancer is high dietary salt intake.

The noteworthy point in the studies is that high salt intake increases CagA levels in *H. pylori* and thus promotes infection. Eradication of *H. pylori* may reduce the risk of gastric cancer, and studies have confirmed that it can reduce the incidence of gastric cancer, including people at high risk of gastric cancer [44].

3.3 H. pylori and insulin resistance

Since the immune system is triggered by *H. pylori* infection, some inflammatory cytokines such as tumor necrosis factor α (TNF- α), leptin, and adipokines create an immune response to this inflammation. Relevant studies have revealed that leptin deficiency can induce insulin resistance (IR) to high levels of TNF- α and IL-6. Inflammatory cytokines induce phosphorylation of serine residues on the insulin receptor substrate, which causes disruption of insulin function and disruption of substrate interaction with insulin receptors. Consequently, diabetes can occur with deterioration of blood glucose regulation.[45]

Treatment of H. pylori infection

The infection is treated with a combination of antimicrobial and antisecretory agents, and the intestinal pH must be increased with antisecretory agents to achieve the bactericidal effect of the antimicrobial agents. Alternatively, herbal medicines and probiotics are used as complementary therapy to help eradicate *H. pylori*, although their mechanism of action is not yet clear. [46] The increasing prevalence of antimicrobial resistance in *H. pylori* from person to person has led to failure of eradication therapy with decreased adherence to clinical nutrition therapies. In the treatment of *H. pylori*, drug resistance can easily develop against antibiotics used alone, so the recommended treatment is a combination of several antibiotics. Several antimicrobial agents, antisecretory agents, and proton pump inhibitors are used in the treatment protocol for *H. pylori*, including clarithromycin, amoxicillin, levofloxacin, metronidazole, tetracycline, rifabutin, and bismuth-containing compounds. According to many international guidelines, the first-line treatment for *H. pylori* infection is triple therapy consisting of the antibiotic clarithromycin given for 7-14 days, with any

antibiotic of amoxicillin or metronidazole, and a proton pump inhibitor or ranitidine bismuth citrate. If treatment is unsuccessful, second-line therapy is initiated. This therapy is given according to individual antibiotic resistance and sensitivities, or empirically. Second-line therapy is usually defined as tetracycline, metronidazole, bismuth salt, or a proton pump inhibitor. After failure of second-line therapy, antimicrobial susceptibility testing should be performed on *H. pylori* cultures from which gastric biopsy was taken, objective antibiotic resistance should be considered, and therapy should be continued. It has also been reported that proton pump inhibitors, which have been used for a long time in the treatment of *H. pylori* infection, may inhibit the absorption of micronutrients as well as their benefits [47]. The US Food and Drug Administration has suggested that long-term use of proton pump inhibitors may increase the risk of hypomagnesemia and fractures.

H. pylori and nutrition

Helicobacter pylori infection has the major pathogenic effect, especially in upper gastrointestinal diseases. In addition to its cytotoxic and proinflammatory effects, *H. pylori* affect other microorganisms in the gastrointestinal tract, at the gut-gastrointestinal communication, albeit indirectly [48]. It produces various biological effects on hormones such as ghrelin and leptin, which control both growth and appetite, causing changes in appetite and food intake, while causing changes in symptoms and immune responses.

H. pylori is considered a causative factor for malnutrition and growth retardation, especially in childhood, due to poor absorption of nutrients and increased susceptibility to intestinal infections, especially in developing countries. Nweneka et al., in a meta-analysis study, reported that subjects infected with *H. pylori* had lower circulating ghrelin concentrations in 19 studies. On the other hand, eradication of *H. pylori* did not show any significant effect on circulating ghrelin. This discrepancy in results depends on the amount of damage to the hormone-producing cells before resection, the time it takes for these cells to regenerate, and the duration of infection in the circulation. Dietary modification to prevent carcinogenesis promoted by *H. pylori*, which is a risk factor for cancer, should include resection as well as practical strategies for the prevention of gastric cancer. In addition, general nutrition has proven to be very important in nutritional approaches, as many nutrients such as vitamin C, iron, vitamin B12, and vitamin E are known to cause malabsorption and lead to important nutritional consequences.[49]

H. pylori and salt

Helicobacter pylori infection, besides being a pathogenic strain, may not be a sufficient cause for the development of gastric cancer. However, the risk of gastric cancer increases with high salt intake. Epidemiological studies have shown a link between high salt intake and increased risk of gastric cancer in many parts of the world. It has been shown in several studies that high salt intake can affect the interactions between gastric tissue and bacteria, with synergistic effects with *H. pylori*, and increase the possibility of persistent infection. The bacterial oncoprotein CagA may contribute to the formation of gastric cancer by disrupting signaling pathways of gastric epithelial cells. On the other hand, it has been determined that CagA protein indirectly contributes to the pathogenesis of gastric cancer by inducing increased inflammation of the gastric mucosa, as it induces the proinflammatory cytokine IL-8 and causes increased secretion. A study by Gaddi et al. A study of the effects of high salt intake on *H. pylori* infection reported that Mongolian gerbils (*H. pylori* infection causes chronic gastritis, gastric ulcers, and intestinal metaplasia in Mongolian gerbils, thus being the best animal model) were infected with a wild-type strain of CagA + *H. pylori*. Infected animals fed a high-salt diet were reported to have severe gastroenteritis and a higher rate of gastric adenocarcinoma, with increased expression of the proinflammatory cytokines IL-1 β and inducible nitric oxide synthase (iNOS), compared with those fed a normal diet (Figure 1). In addition, Caston et al. identified increased levels of the toxin VacA in the extracellular space in response to high salt in laboratory conditions. These salt-induced changes have been shown to contribute to the increased risk of gastric cancer in *H. pylori*-infected individuals who follow a high-salt diet.[50]

Figure (1): Excessive salt intake may contribute to the formation of stomach cancer by disrupting molecular pathways and some secretions of epithelial cells in the stomach.

H. pylori and iron

Iron is involved in maintaining metabolic functions as a cofactor in biological systems involved in various oxidation-reduction processes, electron transfer, and the synthesis of amino acids and nucleotides, which are essential for life. It is also a very important growth factor for almost all bacteria.

There is usually a race between bacteria and the host to absorb iron. On the other hand, the reaction of iron with free oxygen creates a Fenton reaction, which contributes to the generation of oxygen radicals that can cause serious damage to the structures of cellular biomolecules [51].

H. pylori, a pathogen of gastric tissue, faces a series of environmental stresses in the human stomach where it colonizes. Iron deficiency is expected to occur in the long term and in some at-risk groups (Figure 2), as the human body tightly retains available iron to prevent both bacterial growth and oxidative damage. At the same time, acid secretion resulting from *H. pylori*-induced gastritis can inhibit iron absorption and cause deficiency [52].

Iron deficiency, which causes *H. pylori* infection, is thought to be also effective in *H. pylori* virulence (Fig. 2). In support of this, an in vitro study found that iron deficiency affects *H. pylori* virulence factors, leading to Cag T4SS activity and inhibition of gastric acid secretion by the host with increased expression of IL-8, contributing to the increased incidence and severity of gastroenteritis and, consequently, the development of gastric cancer.[53]

Figure (2): *Helicobacter pylori* and related dietary factors. High salt intake can increase the risk of persistent infection. *Helicobacter pylori* can cause iron deficiency and reduce the bioavailability of vitamin C. Some nutrients (allicin, lycopene, capsaicin, etc.) have positive effects on *Helicobacter pylori*.

H. pylori and vitamin C

Vitamin C is a micronutrient essential for human health. Unlike many animals, humans have lost the ability to biosynthesize vitamin C (ascorbic acid) due to various mutations in the oxidase enzyme [54].

Vitamin C is a chemical reducing agent or electron donor. On the other hand, electrons from ascorbate can reduce metals such as iron and copper, leading to the formation of hydrogen peroxide, superoxide, and reactive oxidative species. As a reducing agent, ascorbate can form oxidants in some cases. While vitamin C protects against oxidative stress in cancer cells through its antioxidant effect, it can also increase the risk of cancer through its pro-oxidant activity [55].

The bioavailability of vitamin C can be significantly reduced by *H. pylori* infection (Figure 2). In support of this, a 1995 study showed that *H. pylori* can oxidize and neutralize ascorbic acid in the stomach. In another study, gastric juice and plasma vitamin C levels were significantly decreased with decreased vitamin C intake in people with *H. pylori*. In such studies, vitamin C levels would be expected to return to normal after *H. pylori* eradication. Atrophic gastritis, which is caused by *H. pylori* and leads to gastric cancer, may disrupt the secretion of vitamin C in the gastric mucosa and increase the pH of gastric juice [56]. In a study by Waring et al., when a control group of 48 gastritis patients without supplements was compared with an experimental group of 32 gastritis patients who were given 500 mg of vitamin C twice daily for 2 weeks, it was found that high vitamin C intake could reduce the risk of gastric cancer, but it was shown that the protective effect may be greater if gastritis is treated with *H. pylori* eradication [57]. In another study, Zojaji et al. divided the study group into two groups, established the same treatment protocol for both groups, and added vitamin C to the second group. The experimental results showed that 78.0% of individuals in the group that received supplemental vitamin C had increased *H. pylori* eradication rates compared to 48.8% of individuals in the other group.

On the other hand, side effects such as gastrointestinal disturbances, especially osmotic diarrhea, may occur due to high doses of vitamin C, and it also causes increased excretion of uric acid and oxalate, and may also be associated with an increased risk of kidney stones caused by calcium oxalate. In rare cases, due to its pro-oxidant activity at high concentrations, especially in supplement form, high concentrations (500 mg/day or more) are expected to cause various adverse effects such as DNA damage and, indirectly, some types of cancer in the presence of high iron stores in the human body.

Given that it is a water-soluble vitamin, coupled with the potential for toxicity from a single daily bolus dose and a short biological half-life, further clinical research is needed to determine the correct dosage [58]. However, vitamin C, generally taken with normal diet, increases mucosal immune responses by scavenging free radicals, particularly through fruit and vegetable consumption. It reduces the N-nitrosamine content of gastric juice and inhibits cell proliferation. It may be particularly protective against *H. pylori*-associated gastric carcinogenesis through a direct effect on *H. pylori* growth.

Treatment

The rate of recovery from *H. pylori* infection usually depends on the age of the infected person and the stability of his health condition. Stomach bacteria are treated with a group of medications for a period of 14 days in most cases, but the period may be longer depending on the case and upon the doctor's recommendation.[32]

The drug treatment options used to treat *H. pylori* include the following:

1- Antibiotics: Antibiotics kill bacteria, including:

- Amoxicillin.
- Clarithromycin.
- Levofloxacin.
- Rifabutin.
- Tetracycline.
- Metronidazole.

2-Proton pump inhibitors: These are medications that reduce stomach acidity.

3-Bismuth Subsalicylate: Bismuth works to coat the ulcer and protect it from stomach acid.[69]

Prevention

Tips to reduce the transmission of stomach bacteria No effective vaccine has yet been developed to prevent infection with stomach bacteria, but some preventive measures can be followed to reduce the risk of infection with stomach bacteria and other different bacteria. The following are some of these measures: Avoid eating undercooked foods. Avoid eating foods and drinks that have not been cleaned well before preparation. Avoid eating foods served by people who have not washed their hands well before serving them. Be sure to wash your hands well after using the toilet and before starting to prepare food, while being sure to teach children to do so as well.[32]

1- You should quit smoking.

2-It is preferable to divide meals into periods of the day so that they are close together, in order to avoid completely emptying the stomach and increasing its acidity.

3-You should stop drinking alcohol.

4- You should drink adequate amounts of water, about 6 cups a day, unless there is a medical contraindication.

About 50% of the world's population is infected with *Helicobacter pylori* in the stomach, and although the causes of the stomach germ are not yet known and there is no vaccine to prevent infection, there are a number of tips that contribute to preventing infection with the stomach germ, such as:

- Avoid caffeine found in coffee and many energy drinks.
- Avoid contaminated foods and drinks.
- Avoid eating any food that is not well cooked or has been prepared by someone who did not wash their hands well.
- Avoid spices and hot foods.
- Avoid psychological pressure and tension.
- Treat digestive system symptoms directly.
- Maintain personal hygiene
- Do not take medical treatments without consulting a doctor, especially aspirin, painkillers, and non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs.

Refined grains such as white bread, white rice, pasta, and grains low in dietary fiber should be replaced with oatmeal, barley, brown rice, and whole wheat bread.

Acidic foods, especially lemons, oranges, citrus juices, tomatoes, pickled products, and vinegar can be replaced with foods that contain high fiber such as mango, papaya, bananas, beans, zucchini, cauliflower, and turnips.

Some nutrition experts indicate that a diet rich in fruits and vegetables and low in sugars may help reduce or stop infection with *H. pylori*.

There are many foods that may be useful for prevention, such as: green tea, cauliflower, garlic, and others.

Promising results have emerged through recent large-scale studies on mice to use an anti-*H. pylori* vaccine . [32]

The possible side effects that a patient may experience when taking medications used to treat *H. pylori* include the following:

- Abdominal pain.
- Dry mouth.
- Increased thirst.
- Constipation.
- Unpleasant taste in the mouth.
- Dark stool color.
- Increased itching in the vaginal area in women, and increased secretions.
- Nausea or vomiting.
- Diarrhea.
- Headache.
- Changes in the tongue and its color.

Conclusions

It is estimated that *H. pylori* infects half of the world's population and causes persistent infections as well as many health problems such as gastritis, MALT lymphoma, and peptic ulcer. In *H. pylori* infection, there are some therapeutic limitations due to its ability to create resistance to antibiotic therapies in treatment strategies. Therefore, it has become necessary to search for alternatives to combat *H. pylori* infection. Especially in the past few years, research has clearly shown the pathogenicity, bacterial activity, and genetic predisposition to help understand the severity of gastric atrophy and gastric cancer caused by *H. pylori*. This condition is expected to positively affect the treatment process. Combination therapies, including phytochemicals and probiotics found in natural products, appear to have beneficial effects in eradicating *H. pylori*. Due to the effects of hormones such as ghrelin and leptin, which control both growth and appetite, and the formation of malabsorption of several nutrients such as vitamin C, iron, vitamin B12, and vitamin E in individuals infected with *H. pylori*. Information should be provided during and after treatment. It is important to provide optimal nutrition by identifying strategies and implementing the appropriate diet for the individual by certified nutritionists. In addition, there have been some promising effects of probiotics added to treatment strategies.

Recommendations

1. Detailed research is needed.
2. A diet rich in fruits and vegetables and low in salt and processed meat products has good preventive potential, especially in eliminating *H. pylori*.
3. The need to control the spread of infection through programs to educate citizens through preventive measures such as conducting examinations to detect the disease before blood donation and surgical operations, as well as controlling dental clinics and tattoo shops and not using previously used toothbrushes and razors.
4. There is a need for a comprehensive epidemiological study in Iraq in general to accurately determine the spread and infection rates, as well as the factors that lead to the high spread of infection among citizens. This requires cooperation between the Ministries of Higher Education and Health.

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